

Residual Mexican biomasses for bioenergy and fine-chemicals production: correlation between composition and specific applications

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Abstract

The conversion of renewable biomasses into biofuels and chemicals represents a strategic way to reduce the use of fossil feedstock, by contributing in switching to a more sustainable society. The use of agro-industrial wastes does not subtract resources destined for food consumption. In addition, waste utilization would result in a reduction of its accumulation, with a consequent decrease of environmental impact and financial losses due to the relevant disposal. In this context, a wide variety of exploitable agricultural resources can be used to support this sustainable growth. However, the characterization represents the first step towards a targeted and proficient exploitation of the chemical and energetic potential of a residual biomass. In this work, some representative residual (Mexican) biomasses were investigated: pepper residues (*Hungarian yellow and red variety*), coconut shells (*Cocos Nucifera*), flamboyant pods (*Delonix Regia*), seeds of avocado (*Persea Americana*), palm (*Palma de Coroco*) and nance (*Byrsonima Crassifolia*) were chemically characterized and the relevant potential applications for the synthesis of biofuels and fine chemicals were specifically evaluated. Lipids, structural carbohydrates and lignin were specifically valorized in a proficient cascade of technologies, which aim to exploit the correspondent potential, according to the principles of biorefinery and circular economy.

Keywords

Bioenergy, biorefinery, valorization, waste biomass, biodiesel, circular economy

1 Introduction

As a result of population growth, an increase of the worldwide energy demand will be expected in the next years [1,2]. According to the BP Statistical Review of World Energy 2019 [3], the current global energy consumption was estimated to be of 13 864.9 million tonnes of oil equivalent (Mtoe),

84.7% of which deriving from fossil fuels (oil, coal and natural gas), 6.8% from hydroelectric energy and 4.4% from nuclear energy.

Asia Pacific and North America showed the highest consumption of fossil fuels (about 63.6% of the total energy consumption): China, United States, India and Japan are the major consumers. Maintaining this level of rate of consume of resources, the global reserve are going to be exhausted within the next 50 years. The gradual depletion of fossil fuels and the negative environmental impact on the global climate associated with their use [4], have motivated the search of alternatives for turning to a more sustainable energy production [5,6]. Renewable energies, often referred also as clean or “green” energies, are produced from sources that do not deplete or can be replenished within a human’s lifetime. The most common examples include wind, solar, geothermal and bioenergy derived from biomass [7–9]. Currently, renewable energies constitute only 4% of the global energy consumption, but this sector is expected to grow thanks to the increase of investments and the development of new technologies [3]. The conversion of biomasses into biofuels and biochemicals represent a promising and useful way to mitigate the global warming and diversify the energy sources [10–12]. Biomass is a renewable resource that can be obtained from agricultural residues [13,14], industrial and animal wastes [15,16] and human activity more in general (organic waste, sludge from water treatment plants [17–19], etc.). Differently from fossil feedstock, biomasses are more widely distributed over the Earth's surface and they can be exploited using environmental friendly technologies. In addition, biomass could also be a valuable source of chemicals, pharmaceuticals and food additives [20–22]. In that case, a cascade of technologies aimed of exploiting the overall chemical and energetic potential could be appropriately designed, separating in different streams the different components of high value.

A challenging point related to the biomass valorization is the diverse nature of sources, which completely change with respect to latitude, climatic area and country considered. For this reason, biomasses are really variable and specifically depend from the country. Mexico is a country that expects to enter into the market of bioenergy taking advantage of its climate, orography and variety

of exploitable residual agricultural resources, which are favorable for the production of biofuels, as a sustainable alternative to support economic growth. However, these alternative sources of energy deriving from residual biomasses have not yet been fully exploited. According to the National Energy Balance databases and the Mexican Ministry of Energy (SENER) [23], Mexico produced 189.6 Mtoe during 2018 deriving from the following resources: 44.3 % from oil, 41.1 % from natural gas, 6.4 % from coal, 1.7 % from nuclear energy, 3.9 % from hydroelectric energy and 2.6 % from other renewables (1.5 % from wind, 0.5 % from solar and only 0.6 % from biomass). These data indicate that fossil fuels are predominant, whereas the use of biomass represents only a small proportion of the total. More recently, new significant changes in public policies have been proposing to promote the development of renewable energy. The Mexican General Law for Climate Change aims to generate 35% of its energy needs from renewable energy by 2024 [24]. In addition, the Law for the Use of Renewable Energy and Finance of the Energy Transition (LAERFTE) [25], establishes a further reduction of fossil fuels generation to 50% by 2050 and other rules and conditions for the use of renewable energy are introduced. In any case, in order to respect sustainability criteria, biomasses to be used in bioenergy generation needs to satisfy several issues. In general, it is assumed that their production do not compete with food crops and also indirect negative impact on the environment should be evaluated (deforestation and/or inappropriate use of land). Excluding dedicated cultivation, identification of biomasses to be used for the production of bioenergy needs to take care of the prompt availability criteria. Agro-industrial processing produces considerable waste, particularly residue achieved from seeds, pods and shells; which can cause environmental problems and financial losses due to the relevant high costly disposal. Therefore, efforts are underway to develop integrated strategies to promote these residues. A particular attention was dedicated to the lipidic component and the relevant conversion into biodiesel, namely fatty acid methyl esters (FAME). Typically, FAME are produced by transesterification of glycerides contained into natural resources such as vegetable oil or animal fats with methanol [26,27]. It is a clean renewable fuel, which has chemical and physical properties similar with respect to the fossil

fuels [28,29]. In addition, it is biodegradable, oxygenated and free of sulfur with a consequently reduced gas emission compared to petroleum derivatives [30,31]. Biodiesel production is attracting the attention of Mexican government agencies, as it can promote regional development in the country supporting the diversification of agriculture practices and industrial activities. In 2008, the Mexican Congress approved the Bioenergetics Act that favors the use of biodiesel and bioethanol in diesel and gasoline sell in Mexico by Petróleos Mexicanos (PEMEX), the State-owned company that produces, refines, and transforms the crude oil. It should replace 7.8% of conventional diesel consumption by 2031 [32]. In order to contain manufacturing costs and to promote the economic development, the use of refined edible oils as raw materials for biodiesel production in direct competition with the food industry must be replaced by non-edible waste materials with high diversity and availability. Six industrial plants located in the states of Chiapas, Michoacán and Nuevo León in Mexico were designed to process waste vegetable oils, castor oil and animal tallow [33].

In this work, a study of the valorization of some of the main Mexican biomass wastes was carried out, in order to identify their potential applications for the production of fuels and value-added chemicals. In detail, pepper residues, coconut shells, flamboyant pods, seeds of avocado, palm and nance were analyzed and fully characterized, evaluating their possible exploitation through a cascade of technologies. Lipids can mainly find application in the field of biodiesel production, whereas structural carbohydrates and lignin can produce biofuels (ethyl levulinate, bioethanol, biogas, etc.) and fine-chemicals (biomaterials, platform molecules, biochar, adsorbent, etc.). Biorefination of the aforementioned residual biomasses were proposed with the aim of using all their components in a profitable way and reducing the final waste, in coherence with the circular economy principles.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Reagents and instruments

All chemical reagents used in this work were of analytical grade and were used directly without further purification or treatment. Peppers residues (*Hungarian yellow and red variety*), coconut shells (*Cocos Nucifera*), flamboyant pods (*Delonix Regia*), seeds of avocado (*Persea Americana*), palm (*Palma de Coroco*) and nance (*Byrsonima Crassifolia*) were purchased from a local market of Aguascalientes (Mexico). Then, the sample were immediately processed (within two days) avoiding long time of conservation (298 K). FAME were identified by gas chromatography-mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) by using a Perking Elmer Clarus 500 equipped with a Clarus spectrometer. Quantitative determinations were carried out with a Varian 3800 GC-FID. Both instruments were configured for cold on-column injections with a HP-5MS capillary column (30 m; Ø 0.32 mm; 0.25 µm film).

Scanning electron microscopy-energy dispersive X-ray (SEM-EDX) analysis were carried out with FEI Quanta 3D FEG equipment under high vacuum conditions, using secondary electron (SE) and backscattered electron (BSED) detectors. Analyses were performed at 20 kV, working distance of 9.7 mm and adopting different magnification power of images.

2.2 Experimental procedure for biomass characterization

2.2.1 Determination of total solids and ashes

Total solids (TS) were determined according to the ISO 11465 method [34]. 10 g of biomass were placed in an oven at 378 K for 24 h, until a constant weight was obtained. Then, the dried samples were heated in a muffle furnace at 823 K for 3 h and ashes content was also determined. The results were expressed as weight percentage (%wt) of residual solids obtained after each thermal treatment, respect to the starting material.

2.2.2 Extraction of raw oils

In a Falcon tube of 50 mL, 5 g of dried biomass were placed with 20 mL of hexane. The system was closed and shaken for 10 min. A biphasic system was obtained: i) an organic phase in which raw oil and grease were dissolved therein and ii) a lower phase of wet solid. The organic phase was then separated from the residual biomass and recovered. The extraction procedure was repeated other three times and all the organic fractions were collected together. Finally, the solvent was evaporated under nitrogen flow and raw oil was weighed and analyzed in terms of acid value, saponifiable lipids, fatty acid profile and average molecular weight (AMW).

2.2.3 Determination of saponifiable lipids

Saponifiable lipids were determined according to the ISO 3657 procedure [35] and gas-chromatographically by using tricaprin (Aldrich, $\geq 99\%$) as internal standard. The results obtained were expressed as weight percentage (%wt) with respect to the starting material.

2.2.4 Determination of acid value

In a flask of 250 mL, 1 g of raw oil was placed with 100 mL of diethyl-ether:ethanol solution (1:1 v/v) in presence of phenolphthalein as indicator. Then, the organic mixture was titrated with 0.1 N KOH solution to the phenolphthalein endpoint. The results were expressed as milligrams of KOH required to neutralize 1 g of raw oil (mg KOH/g).

2.2.5 Fatty acid profile and determination of AMW

20 mg of raw oil and 2 mL of toluene, methanol and concentrated H₂SO₄ (2:2:0.01 v/v/v) were placed in a glass tube of 10 mL. The system was closed and heated at 343 K for 5 h. Then, 1 mL of 1000 ppm methyl heptadecanoate toluene solution was added as internal standard and the resultant solution was analyzed. AMW was determined according to the following equation:

$$AMW = \frac{\sum A_i MW_i}{\sum A_i} \quad (1)$$

where A_i and MW_i are the area and molecular weight of free fatty acids (FFAs), respectively.

2.2.6 Determination of structural carbohydrates and lignin

NREL method for “Determination of Structural Carbohydrates and Lignin in Biomass” was partially adapted and applied on residual dried samples in order to evaluate the content and the composition of simple and structural complex sugars [36]. In detail, by using different hydrolytic solutions, with increasing acidic strength, it was possible to identify and quantify separately simple sugars, from hemicelluloses, starches and pectinic sugars, from cellulosic component. 2 g of residual dried solids (after extraction procedure with hexane) were suspended into 100 mL of 4% wt H_2SO_4 and stirred at room temperature for 1 h. 2 mL of this suspension was filtered, opportunely diluted if necessary and analyzed for determination of free sugars (glucose, fructose and saccharose were overall found). Then, the suspension was refluxed for 4 h. The resultant cooled suspension was filtered: limp solution was brought again to 100 mL of mQ water, diluted if necessary and analyzed, by allowing hemicelluloses, starches and pectinic sugars to be determined. On the other side, the solid filtered from the suspension was washed with over 100 mL of mQ water, dried at 378 K for 24 h and weighted. 0.2 g of this residue was suspended and kept under agitation at 277 K for 24 h in 3 mL of 72% H_2SO_4 . Then, it was brought to 100 mL with mQ water, the resulting solution was transferred into a 250 mL glass balloon and kept under reflux for 4 h. The suspension was cooled and filtered on a filter previously prepared and weighted. The clear solution was diluted if necessary and analyzed for sugars determinations. Finally, filtered solids were abundantly washed with mQ water and dried at 378 K for 24 h and weighted. Insoluble lignin was calculated by the difference between this weight and the respective ashes obtained after putting the same filtering crucible into an oven at 823 K for 3 h.

3 Results and discussion

The production trends for the residual Mexican biomasses investigated in the present work are reported in Fig. 1 [37].

Fig. 1

In the 2017, 3.29 million tonnes (Mt) of peppers, 2.03 Mt of avocado, 1.26 Mt of coconut, 1.15 Mt of palm, 0.87 Mt of nance and 0.51 Mt of flamboyant were harvested in Mexico. In addition, Fig. 1 shows that production of pepper residues, avocado seeds and palm seeds have been doubled in the last ten years, and this trend looks to still continue to increase in the next future. The chemical composition of these Mexican biomass wastes were experimentally determined and results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Water content, TS values and oily component were experimentally evaluated: peppers contained the highest water amount (>93.7 %), followed by avocado seeds (44.4 %) and palm seeds (10 %). Palm seeds show the highest oil content (48.5 %wt), while differently from flamboyant pods and coconut shells, for which no lipids were detected, oil contents in the other biomasses ranged between 2.3 and 6.3 %wt. In order to evaluate the valorization of these lipids, a detailed chemical characterization was carried out in terms of acid value, saponifiable lipids, fatty acid profile and AMW of FFAs. The results are reported in Table 2.

Table 2

Saponifiable lipids represent the main component by exceeding in some cases 70 %wt of the extracted components. While the FFAs profile was almost the same for peppers residue, avocado seeds and nance, in the case of palm seeds, the average molecular weights dropped down sensibly. Short acids have particular physicochemical properties, at the point that their use as conventional biodiesel may be not properly advantageous. On the contrary, methyl esters of C12-C14 organic acids may find application as perfumes and fine chemicals.

In most of cases, the extracted oils are characterized by the presence of high free acidity which ranged between 1 and 15 mg KOH/g. These type of bio-oils can be efficiently converted into the relevant methyl esters by adopting a two-step approach [15]. In the first step, free acidity can be converted into FAME through direct esterification operated under $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ catalysis, while pretreated oil can be subsequently completely converted into the respective methyl esters through a transesterification mediated by alkaline catalysts (NaOH). Final products resulted in any case enriched by the presence of several biogenic compounds, which can be considered as value added components. Sterols (beta-sitosterol), waxes and terpenic structures resulted also significantly present into the raw oily extracts and were found unmodified after the abovementioned upgrading procedure of saponifiable component. Beta-sitosterol is mainly present in all the vegetal residue characterized: 2-4 %wt of lipid extracted (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2

In avocado seeds, in particular, a large amount of the extracted raw-oil were terpenoids. Terpenoids belong to a particular class of terpenes characterized by the presence of several functional groups [38]. These natural compounds have been identified in the raw oils extracted from biomass wastes through GC-MS analysis. From MS spectra reported in Fig. 3, it is possible to observe the typical fragmentation patterns of two different classes of terpenoids with fragment ions located at m/z 81 and 94, respectively, as reported in literature [39–41].

Fig. 3

These biologically active compounds can be used for the treatment of several diseases [42,43], and could play a key role in the production of foods, perfumes, cosmetics and drugs [44]. Under these conditions, after conversion of saponifiable fraction into FAME, the best valorization approach would consist in a purification and separation of pure FAME from sterols, terpenoids and waxes in different streams, which can find specific appropriate applications. Such a separation was positively achieved through a distillation under vacuum: FAME were purely separated at 150-170 °C at 50

mm of Hg, obtaining a stream, which satisfied EN14214 standards. On the other hand, terpenoids were efficiently separated at 170-190 °C and sterols mainly remain as residue of distillation with waxes.

Once that lipid phase was recovered and valorized, structural carbohydrates and lignin remained to be processed. These residual biomasses could represent a paradigm of the most abundant natural feedstocks, since cellulose, together with hemicellulose and lignin, constitute the major components in most of biomass wastes. Cellulose and hemicellulose can be hydrolyzed into pentoses and hexoses, and the resultant hydrolysates can find several application in the field of bioenergy. Besides production of biogas through anaerobic digestion mediated by microorganisms, also liquid biofuels can be efficiently achieved. In fact, ethanol can be produced by fermentation of carbohydrates present in these biomass wastes, in similar way to those used to obtain bioethanol of first generation [45,46]. According to OECD-FAO [47], Mexico produced 108.8 million liters (ML) of ethanol in 2018, and it is projected to reach 133.2 ML by 2026 (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4

Presently, the ethanol production mainly comes from sugar cane and maize fermentation [47]; however, it is not enough to meet the potential energy demand. Obtainment of bioethanol from biomass wastes would prevent the use of natural resources coming from other countries, by improving the national economy. In detail, considering that pepper residues and avocado seeds mainly contained easily hydrolysable sugars, starch-like components of about 50 % of their total dry weight (Table 2), they can represent very valuable and profitable alternatives. According to the availability data of residual biomasses reported into Fig. 1 and average composition reported in Table 2, the bioethanol potentially produced by avocado seeds and peppers residues would be accounted to 75-100 ML.

In addition, more recently, carbohydrates can also be seen as a source of platform molecules: in fact, simple sugars can be further dehydrated into furfural and 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF)

[48–50]. Furfural can be used as a starting material for the synthesis of a series of derivatives including furan, furfuryl alcohol, furoic acid, tetrahydrofuran, 2-methyltetrahydrofuran and related resins [51,52]. HMF is the precursor of 2,5-furandicarboxylic acid (FDCA), one of the top ten value-added biobased chemical listed by the US Department of Energy [53] and an important precursor of bioderivable plastics (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5

FDCA [54,55] can potentially replace petrochemical-derived terephthalic acid. On the other hand, HMF can be converted into dimethylfuran [56], which has applications as fuel and solvent or may be hydrated to produce levulinic acid (LA), a promising platform molecule obtainable under acidic conditions [57,58]. LA can be used for the production of pharmaceuticals, solvents, fuel and oil additives, and plasticizers. Moreover, it can be transformed into alkyl levulinate esters through esterification with alcohols [59], for the production of food additives or fragrances. In addition, LA can be converted into succinic acid and γ -valerolactone (GVL) by oxidation [60] and hydrogenation [61], respectively. GVL is another platform molecule, which can even be converted to adipic acid, which is a precursor for Nylon, opening the possibility for the production of biopolymers [62] to be used in a wide range of applications (foams, fibers and packaging).

Finally, lignin still remain as a residue. Specifically, in the case of coconut shells, nance seeds and flamboyant pods, lignin is the main component (48.5-74.1% wt). Very recently lignin based biomasses have been tested as possible precursors for the production of biochars, which can be largely used as bioadsorbents. The application of bioadsorbents in the environmental treatment of industrial and municipal wastewater has been becoming a significant research area in the recent years [63,64]. Heavy metal ions are reported as main pollutants, due to their toxicity and mobility in the natural water ecosystems. They are stable environmental contaminants and cannot be degraded or destroyed. Several treatment technologies have been developed for the removal of heavy metals from water and wastewater by including: chemical precipitation, oxidation, solvent extraction,

electro dialysis, reverse osmosis, flotation, flocculation, filtration, sedimentation, etc. [65,66]. However, most of these methods have drawbacks, such as manufacturing costs that are not suitable for industries. Activated carbon has been widely used as adsorbent for the removal of heavy metals from wastewater, thanks to the high porosity and mechanical strength [67]. But also in this case, the relatively high cost is a damper for a full exploitation. The necessity of safe and economical methods for the treatment of contaminated waters led to the production of low-cost alternatives respect to the commercial products. Biomass wastes can be efficiently used directly [68], or as precursors for the preparation of bioadsorbents and employed for the adsorption of heavy metals like lead, copper, chromium, mercury, cadmium, arsenic, nickel and other metals, which has a potentially damaging effect on human health (Table 3).

Table 3

Nance, coconut shell and flamboyant pods may have potential in this application. Fig. 6 shows the surface of these materials, which already have a high carbon (aromatic) content, functionalized with hydroxyls and carboxylic acids that can efficiently bind metals.

Fig. 6

In addition, these residual biomasses can be easily upgraded to biochar, after an appropriate thermal treatment, resulting in cheap adsorbents. Fig. 7 shows the effect of pyrolysis carried out at 900 °C under nitrogen flow on the nature of the surface: alveolar morphology was generated, whose removal capacity resulted improved, similar to that one of conventional activated carbon.

Fig. 7

As can be seen in Table 3, biochars exhibit high adsorption capacities of heavy metals similar to those observed for the main commercial activated carbons. Biochars result to be as new potential cost-effective and environmentally-friendly carbon materials with great application in the wastewater treatment. Compared with traditional activated carbons, the main advantage is the wide

availability of feedstocks at low cost. By replacing the more expensive commercial adsorbents with low-cost bioadsorbents (e.g., 246 \$ ton⁻¹ of biochar compared to 1500 \$ ton⁻¹ of activated carbon [88]), a drastic reduction of treatment costs can be achieved. In addition, treatment costs can be even reduced through their possible reuse after a regeneration step. In fact, regeneration procedures have been also positively evaluated, allowing not only the re-use of biochars to be obtained, but also the concomitant separation and recovery of heavy metals to be achieved in a separated stream [89]. Once that the specific uptake does not meet the minimum technical performance anymore, exhausted biochars can be used to produce ash as substitute agricultural lime for raising soil pH [90]. The cost advantage of this technology would guarantee a strong penetration of the Mexican market and in the heavy metal polluting industries.

4 Conclusions

Pepper residues (*Hungarian yellow and red variety*), coconut shells (*Cocos Nucifera*), flamboyant pods (*Delonix Regia*), seeds of avocado (*Persea Americana*), palm (*Palma de Coroco*) and nance (*Byrsonima Crassifolia*) were studied as versatile feedstocks for the production of biofuels and biochemicals. The use of these agricultural residues would allow the reduction of a significant fraction of the fossil fuels currently used, without any competition with foods. After a detailed characterization, several valorization strategies were proposed and verified. Harnessing the available energy from crop residues could potentially lead to the generation of biodiesel and bioethanol, by satisfying the needs for liquid and gaseous fuels, which could not be obtained by other renewable resources. Furthermore, the conversion of structural carbohydrates into fine chemicals (furfural, HMF and derivatives) represent an innovative method for the valorization of such resources, opening the way for new markets. Finally, the application of the lignin component as bioadsorbents in the treatment of industrial and municipal wastewaters would also lead to a further economic advantage and high environmental benefits. Such an approach, if applied on a full

scale, could lead to a sustainable economy progress, according to the principles of the circular economy, not only in the Mexican context, but also in everywhere these specific biomasses are produced. Latina America countries, as well as South-Est Asian countries would significantly benefit of these unexplored source of chemicals, implementing their own biorefinery scenario.

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References

- [1] Tripathi AD, Mishra R, Maurya KK, Singh RB, Wilson DW (2018) Estimates for world population and global food availability for global health. In: *The Role of Functional Food Security in Global Health*, Academic Press, pp. 3–24.
- [2] Khalili S, Rantanen E, Bogdanov D, Breyer C (2019) Global Transportation Demand Development with Impacts on the Energy Demand and Greenhouse Gas Emissions in a Climate-Constrained World. *Energies* 12:3870. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12203870>
- [3] Full report – BP Statistical Review of World Energy (2019). <https://www.bp.com/content/dam/bp/business-sites/en/global/corporate/pdfs/energy-economics/statistical-review/bp-stats-review-2019-full-report.pdf>
Accessed 30 October 2019.
- [4] Martins F, Felgueiras C, Smitkova M, Caetano N (2019) Analysis of fossil fuel energy consumption and environmental impacts in European countries. *Energies* 12:964. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12060964>
- [5] Sequeira TN, Santos MS (2018) Renewable energy and politics: A systematic review and new evidence. *J Clean Prod* 192:553–568. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.04.190>

- [6] Bauwens T, Devine-Wright P (2018) Positive energies? An empirical study of community energy participation and attitudes to renewable energy. *Energ Policy* 118:612–625.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2018.03.062>
- [7] Panwar NL, Kaushik SC, Kothari S (2011) Role of renewable energy sources in environmental protection: A review. *Renew Sust Energ Rev* 15:1513–1524.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2010.11.037>
- [8] Demirbas A (2009) Global renewable energy projections. *Energ Sources Part B* 4:212–224.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15567240701620499>
- [9] Menegaki A (2008) Valuation for renewable energy: a comparative review. *Renew Sust Energ Rev* 12:2422–2437. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2007.06.003>
- [10] Gaurav N, Sivasankari S, Kiran GS, Ninawe A, Selvin J (2017) Utilization of bioresources for sustainable biofuels: A Review. *Renew Sust Energ Rev* 73:205–214.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.01.070>
- [11] Ghosh D, Dasgupta D, Agrawal D, Kaul S, Adhikari DK, Kurmi AK, Arya PK, Bangwal D, Negi MS (2015) Fuels and Chemicals from Lignocellulosic Biomass: An Integrated Biorefinery Approach. *Energ Fuel* 29:3149–3157.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.energyfuels.5b00144>
- [12] Gautam K, Gupta NC, Sharma DK (2014) Physical characterization and comparison of biodiesel produced from edible and non-edible oils of *Madhuca indica* (mahua), *Pongamia pinnata* (karanja), and *Sesamum indicum* (til) plant oilseeds. *Biomass Conv Bioref* 4:193–200. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-013-0101-7>
- [13] Nzihou A (2010) Toward the valorization of waste and biomass. *Renew Sust Energ Rev* 1:3–7. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12649-010-9014-x>
- [14] Chum HL, Overend RP (2001) Biomass and renewable fuels. *Fuel Process Technol* 71:187–195. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-3820\(01\)00146-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-3820(01)00146-1)

- [15] di Bitonto L, Pastore C (2019) Metal hydrated-salts as efficient and reusable catalysts for pre-treating waste cooking oils and animal fats for an effective production of biodiesel. *Renew Energ* 143:1193–1200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2019.05.100>
- [16] Rashama C, Ijoma G, Matambo T (2019) Biogas generation from by-products of edible oil processing: a review of opportunities, challenges and strategies. *Biomass Conv Bioref* 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-019-00385-6>
- [17] di Bitonto L, Lopez A, Mascolo G, Mininni G, Pastore C (2016) Efficient solvent-less separation of lipids from municipal wet sewage scum and their sustainable conversion into biodiesel. *Renew Energ* 90:55–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2015.12.049>
- [18] Simell P, Hannula I, Tuomi S, Nieminen M, Kurkela E, Hiltunen I, Kaisalo N, Kilhlman J (2014) Clean syngas from biomass—process development and concept assessment. *Biomass Conv Bioref* 4: 357–370. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-014-0121-y>
- [19] Pastore C, Lopez A, Mascolo G (2014). Efficient conversion of brown grease produced by municipal wastewater treatment plant into biofuel using aluminium chloride hexahydrate under very mild conditions. *Bioresour Technol* 155:91–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2013.12.106>
- [20] Varma RS (2019) Biomass-Derived Renewable Carbonaceous Materials for Sustainable Chemical and Environmental Applications. *ACS Sustain Chem Eng* 7:6458–6470. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.8b06550>
- [21] Zhou CH, Xia X, Lin CX, Tong DS, Beltramini J (2011) Catalytic conversion of lignocellulosic biomass to fine chemicals and fuels. *Chem Soc Rev* 40:5588–5617. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C1CS15124J>
- [22] Gallezot P (2007) Catalytic routes from renewables to fine chemicals. *Catal Today* 121:76–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2006.11.019>
- [23] SENER. National Energy Balance (2018). <https://www.gob.mx/sener/en>. Accessed 30 October 2019.

- [24] Policy brief Mexico's General Law on Climate Change: Successes and challenges (2019). www.lse.ac.uk/GranthamInstitute/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/Policy_brief_Mexico's-General-Law-on-Climate-Change-Successes-and-challenges_8pp_AverchenkovaGuzman-2.pdf. Accessed 30 October 2019.
- [25] LAERFTE. Law for the Use of Renewable Energy and Finance of the Energy Transition (2019). <https://www.iea.org/policiesandmeasures/pams/mexico/name-24706-en.php>. Accessed 30 October 2019.
- [26] Baskar G, Aiswarya R (2016) Trends in catalytic production of biodiesel from various feedstocks. *Renew Sust Energ Rev* 57:496–504. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.12.101>
- [27] Tubino M, Junior JGR, Bauerfeldt GF (2016) Biodiesel synthesis: A study of the triglyceride methanolysis reaction with alkaline catalysts. *Catal Comm* 75:6–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catcom.2015.10.033>
- [28] Borugadda VB, Goud VV (2012) Biodiesel production from renewable feedstocks: Status and opportunities. *Renew Sust Energ Rev* 16:4763–4784. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.04.010>
- [29] Srivastava A, Prasad R (2000) Triglycerides-based diesel fuels. *Renew Sust Energ Rev* 4:111–133. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1364-0321\(99\)00013-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1364-0321(99)00013-1)
- [30] Buyukkaya E (2010) Effects of biodiesel on a DI diesel engine performance, emission and combustion characteristics. *Fuel* 89:3099–3105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2010.05.034>.
- [31] Szybist JP, Song J, Alam M, Boehman AL (2007) Biodiesel combustion, emissions and emission control. *Fuel Process Technol* 88:679–691. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2006.12.008>
- [32] Ruiz HA, Martínez A, Vermerris W (2016) Bioenergy potential, energy crops, and biofuel production in Mexico. *Bioenerg Res* 9:981–984. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12155-016-9802-7>

- [33] Montero G, Stoytcheva M, Coronado M, García C, Cerezo J, Toscano L, Vázquez AM, León JA (2015) An overview of biodiesel production in Mexico (Vol. 19). In: *Biofuels Status and Perspective*. Krzysztof Biernat, Croatia.
- [34] ISO 11465 (1993) Soil Quality e Determination of Dry Matter and Water Content on a Mass Basis and Gravimetric Method.
- [35] ISO 3657 (2013) Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of saponification value.
- [36] NREL Technical Report/TP-510-42618 (2012) Determination of Structural Carbohydrates and Lignin in Biomass.
- [37] FAOSTAT. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (2019).
<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QC>
- [38] Kolekar SM, Jain BU, Kondawarkar MS (2019) A Review on Steroids and Terpenoids (Stereochemistry, Structural Elucidation, Isolation of Steroids and Terpenoids). *RJPDF* 11:126–130. <https://doi.org/10.5958/0975-4377.2019.00020.X>
- [39] Delazar A, Reid RG, Sarker SD (2004) GC-MS analysis of the essential oil form oleoresin of *Pistacia atlantica* VAR. *mutica*. *Chem Nat Comp* 40:24–27.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/B:CONC.0000025459.72590.9e>
- [40] Scora RW, Ahmed M (1993). Terpenes of *Persea tolimanensis* (Lauraceae), an ancestor of the Guatemalan avocados. *J Agr Food Chem* 41:1971–1973. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf00035a029>
- [41] Omeje KO, Ozioko JN, Opmeje HC (2018) Pharmacological Potentials, Characterization and Fatty Acids Profile of *Persea americana* Mill. (Avocado) Seed Oil Using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy. *Biochem Anal Biochem* 7:2161–1009.
<https://doi.org/10.4172/2161-1009.1000361>
- [42] Roy DN (2019) In: *Terpenoids Against Human Diseases*, CRC Press
- [43] Rabi T, Bishayee A (2019) Terpenoids and breast cancer chemoprevention. *Breast Cancer Res Tr* 115:223–239. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10549-008-0118-y>

- [44] di Bitonto L, Todisco S, Gallo V, Pastore C (2020) Urban sewage scum and primary sludge as profitable sources of biodiesel and biolubricants of new generation. *Bioresour Technol Rep*, in press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biteb.2020.100382>.
- [45] Murphy JD, McCarthy K (2005) Ethanol production from energy crops and wastes for use as a transport fuel in Ireland. *Appl Energ* 82:148–166.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2004.10.004>
- [46] Dermibas A (2005) Bioethanol from cellulosic materials: a renewable motor fuel from biomass. *Energ. Source* 27:327–337. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00908310390266643>
- [47] OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook 2017-2026 (2019)
<https://stats.oecd.org/index.aspx?queryid=76849#>. Accessed 30 October 2019.
- [48] Dutta S, Pal S (2014) Promises in direct conversion of cellulose and lignocellulosic biomass to chemicals and fuels: Combined solvent–nanocatalysis approach for biorefinery. *Bioenerg Res* 62:182–197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2013.12.019>
- [49] Van de Vyver S, Geboers J, Jacobs PA, Sels BF (2011) Recent advances in the catalytic conversion of cellulose. *ChemCatChem* 3:82–94. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cctc.201000302>
- [50] Su Y, Brown HM, Huang X, Zhou XD, Amonette JE, Zhang ZC (2009) Single-step conversion of cellulose to 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), a versatile platform chemical. *Appl Catal A Gen* 361:117–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcata.2009.04.002>
- [51] Mariscal R, Maireles-Torres P, Ojeda M, Sádaba I, Granados ML (2016) Furfural: a renewable and versatile platform molecule for the synthesis of chemicals and fuels. *Energ Environ Sci* 9:1144–1189. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5EE02666K>
- [52] Lange JP, Van Der Heide E, van Buijtenen J, Price R (2012) Furfural—a promising platform for lignocellulosic biofuels. *ChemSusChem* 5:150–166.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.201100648>

- [53] Bozell JJ, Petersen GR (2010) Technology development for the production of biobased products from biorefinery carbohydrates—the US Department of Energy’s “Top 10” revisited. *Green Chem* 12:539–554. <https://doi.org/10.1039/B922014C>
- [54] Van Nguyen C, Liao YT, Kang TC, Chen JE, Yoshikawa T, Nakasaka Y, Masuda T, Wu KCW (2016) A metal-free, high nitrogen-doped nanoporous graphitic carbon catalyst for an effective aerobic HMF-to-FDCA conversion. *Green Chem* 18:5957–5961. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6GC02118B>
- [55] Lolli A, Albonetti S, Utili L, Amadori R, Ospitali F, Lucarelli C, Cavani F (2015) Insights into the reaction mechanism for 5-hydroxymethylfurfural oxidation to FDCA on bimetallic Pd–Au nanoparticles. *Appl Catal A Gen* 504:408–419. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcata.2014.11.020>
- [56] Jung D, Körner P, Kruse A (2019) Kinetic study on the impact of acidity and acid concentration on the formation of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), humins, and levulinic acid in the hydrothermal conversion of fructose. *Biomass Conv Bioref* 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-019-00507-0>
- [57] di Bitonto L, Locaputo V, D'Ambrosio V, Pastore C (2020) Direct Lewis-Brønsted acid ethanolysis of sewage sludge for production of liquid fuels. *Appl Energ* 259:114163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.114163>.
- [58] Rackemann DW, Doherty WO (2011) The conversion of lignocellulosics to levulinic acid. *Biofuel Bioprod Bior* 5:198–214. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bbb.267>
- [59] di Bitonto L, Antonopoulou G, Braguglia C, Campanale C, Gallipoli A, Lyberatos G, Ntaikou I, Pastore C (2018) Lewis-Brønsted acid catalysed ethanolysis of the organic fraction of municipal solid waste for efficient production of biofuels. *Bioresour Technol* 266:297–305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2018.06.110>

- [60] Corbel-Demaiilly L, Ly BK, Minh DP, Tapin B, Especel C, Epron F, Cabiac A, Guillon E, Besson M, Pinel C (2013) Heterogeneous catalytic hydrogenation of biobased levulinic and succinic acids in aqueous solutions. *ChemSusChem* 6:2388–2395.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.201300608>
- [61] Alonso DM, Gallo JMR, Mellmer MA, Wettstein SG, Dumesic JA (2013) Direct conversion of cellulose to levulinic acid and gamma-valerolactone using solid acid catalysts. *Catal Sci Technol* 3:927–931. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C2CY20689G>
- [62] Lange JP, Vestering JZ, Haan RJ (2007) Towards ‘bio-based’ Nylon: conversion of γ -valerolactone to methyl pentenoate under catalytic distillation conditions. *Chem Comm* 33:3488–3490. <https://doi.org/10.1039/B705782B>
- [63] Sud D, Mahajan G, Kaur MP (2008) Agricultural waste material as potential adsorbent for sequestering heavy metal ions from aqueous solutions—A review. *Bioresour Technol* 99:6017–6027. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2007.11.064>
- [64] Mohan D, Sarswat A, Ok YS, Pittman Jr CU (2014) Organic and inorganic contaminants removal from water with biochar, a renewable, low cost and sustainable adsorbent—a critical review. *Bioresour Technol* 160:191–202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2014.01.120>
- [65] Gunatilake SK (2015) Methods of removing heavy metals from industrial wastewater. *Methods* 1:12–18. JMESSP13420004.
- [66] di Bitonto L, Volpe A, Pagano M, Bagnuolo G, Mascolo G, La Parola V, Di Leo P, Pastore C (2017) Amorphous boron-doped sodium titanates hydrates: Efficient and reusable adsorbents for the removal of Pb^{2+} from water. *J Hazard Mater* 324:168–177.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2016.10.046>
- [67] Babel S, Kurniawan TA (2004) Cr (VI) removal from synthetic wastewater using coconut shell charcoal and commercial activated carbon modified with oxidizing agents and/or chitosan. *Chemosphere* 54:951–967. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2003.10.001>

- [68] Tejada-Tovar C, Gonzalez-Delgado AD, Villabona-Ortiz A (2019) Characterization of Residual Biomasses and Its Application for the Removal of Lead Ions from Aqueous Solution. *Appl Sci* 9:4486. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9214486>
- [69] Díaz-Muñoz LL, Bonilla-Petriciolet A, Reynel-Ávila HE, Mendoza-Castillo DI (2016) Sorption of heavy metal ions from aqueous solution using acid-treated avocado kernel seeds and its FTIR spectroscopy characterization. *J Mol Liq* 215:555–564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2016.01.022>
- [70] Amuda OS, Giwa A, Bello IA (2007) Removal of heavy metal from industrial wastewater using modified activated coconut shell carbon. *Biochem Eng J* 36:174–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2007.02.013>
- [71] Kadirvelu K, Namasivayam C (2003) Activated carbon from coconut coirpith as metal adsorbent: adsorption of Cd (II) from aqueous solution. *Adv Environ Res* 7:471–478. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1093-0191\(02\)00018-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1093-0191(02)00018-7)
- [72] Reynel-Avila HE, Mendoza-Castillo DI, Olumide AA, Bonilla-Petriciolet A (2016) A survey of multi-component sorption models for the competitive removal of heavy metal ions using bush mango and flamboyant biomasses. *J Mol Liq* 224:1041–1054. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2016.10.061>
- [73] Mustapha SI, Adewoye LT, Aderibigbe FA, Alhaji MH, Adekola MI, Tijani IA (2017) Removal of Lead and Chromium from Aqueous Solution onto Flamboyant (*Delonix regia*) Pod Activated Carbon. *Niger J Technol Dev* 14:56–66. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/njtd.v14i2.4>
- [74] Pellerá FM, Giannis A, Kalderis D, Anastasiadou K, Stegmann R, Wang JY, Gidarakos E (2012) Adsorption of Cu(II) ions from aqueous solutions on biochars prepared from agricultural by-products. *J Environ Manage* 96:35–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2011.10.010>

- [75] Kurniawan TA, Chan GY, Lo WH, Babel S (2006) Comparisons of low-cost adsorbents for treating wastewaters laden with heavy metals. *Sci Total Environ* 366:409–426.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2005.10.001>
- [76] Chen X, Chen G, Chen L, Chen Y, Lehmann J, McBride MB, Hay AG (2011) Adsorption of copper and zinc by biochars produced from pyrolysis of hardwood and corn straw in aqueous solution. *Bioresour Technol* 102:8877–8884. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2011.06.078>
- [77] Liu Z, Zhang F (2009) Removal of lead from water using biochars prepared from hydrothermal liquefaction of biomass. *J Hazard Mater* 167:933–939.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2009.01.085>
- [78] Kong H, He J, Gao Y, Wu H, Zhu X (2011) Cosorption of phenanthrene and mercury (II) from aqueous solution by soybean stalk-based biochar. *J Agric Food Chem* 59:12116–12123.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/jf202924a>
- [79] Shawabkeh RA, Rockstraw DA, Bhada RK (2002) Copper and strontium adsorption by a novel carbon material manufactured from pecan shells. *Carbon* 40:781–786.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-6223\(01\)00198-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-6223(01)00198-1)
- [80] Aguayo-Villarreal IA, Bonilla-Petriciolet A, Muñiz-Valencia R (2017) Preparation of activated carbons from pecan nutshell and their application in the antagonistic adsorption of heavy metal ions. *J Mol Liq* 230:686–695. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2017.01.039>
- [81] Witek-Krowiak A, Szafran RG, Modelski S (2011) Biosorption of heavy metals from aqueous solutions onto peanut shell as a low-cost biosorbent. *Desalination* 265:126–134.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2010.07.042>
- [82] Kobya M, Demirbas E, Senturk E, Ince M (2005) Adsorption of heavy metal ions from aqueous solutions by activated carbon prepared from apricot stone. *Bioresour Technol* 96:1518–1521. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2004.12.005>

- [83] Richards S, Dawson J, Stutter M (2019) The potential use of natural vs commercial biosorbent material to remediate stream waters by removing heavy metal contaminants. *J Environ Manage* 231:275–281. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.10.019>
- [84] Kołodyńska D, Krukowska J, Thomas P (2017) Comparison of sorption and desorption studies of heavy metal ions from biochar and commercial active carbon. *Chem Eng J* 307: 353–363. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2016.08.088>
- [85] Kuroki A, Hiroto M, Urushihara Y, Horikawa T, Sotowa K, Avila JRA (2019) Adsorption mechanism of metal ions on activated carbon. *Adsorption* 25:1251–1258. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10450-019-00069-7>
- [86] Velghe I, Carleer R, Yperman J, Schreurs S, D’Haen J (2012) Characterisation of adsorbents prepared by pyrolysis of sludge and sludge/disposal filter cake mix. *Water Res* 46:2783–2794. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2012.02.034>
- [87] Radjenovic A, Medunic G (2015) Removal of Cr(VI) from aqueous solution by a commercial carbon black. *Desalin Water Treat* 55:183–192. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19443994.2014.912966>
- [88] Inyang M, Dickenson E (2015) The potential role of biochar in the removal of organic and microbial contaminants from potable and reuse water: a review. *Chemosphere* 134:232–240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2015.03.072>
- [89] Gupta VK, Nayak A, Agarwal S (2015) Bioadsorbents for remediation of heavy metals: current status and their future prospects. *Environ Eng Res* 20:1-18. <https://doi.org/10.4491/eer.2015.018>
- [90] Kalus K, Koziel JA, Opaliński S (2019) A Review of Biochar Properties and Their Utilization in Crop Agriculture and Livestock Production. *Appl Sci* 9:3494 <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9173494>

Figures

Fig. 1. Production (Mt) for the main Mexican cultivated crops 2000-2017.

Fig. 2. a) GC-MS chromatograms of converted avocado seeds extracts. b) MS-spectra of sterols.

Fig. 3. MS-spectra of terpenoids present in raw oils extracted from biomass wastes.

Fig. 4. Scheme for conversion of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural in platform molecules.

Fig. 5. Future trend of bioethanol production (ML) in Mexico 2018-2026.

Fig. 6. SEM images of a) flamboyant pods, b) coconut shells and c) nance seeds precursors, used as feedstock for biochar synthesis.

Fig. 7. SEM images of biochars obtained from a) avocado seeds and b) flamboyant pods after pyrolysis at 900 °C under a nitrogen flow.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Flamboyant pods

Coconut shells

Nance seeds

Fig. 7

Biochar by Avocado seeds

Biochar by Flamboyant pods

Table 1.

Chemical composition (%wt) of several Mexican biomass wastes.

Biomass wastes	Pepper residues	Avocado seeds	Coconut shells	Palm seeds	Nance seeds	Flamboyant pods
Total solids (%wt)	6.3 ± 0.1	55.6 ± 1.9	93.9 ± 0.1	90.0 ± 0.1	95.8 ± 0.5	92.7 ± 0.2
Chemical composition (%wt)						
Raw oil	2.3 ± 0.1	4.8 ± 0.3	-	49.8 ± 0.5	6.3 ± 0.1	-
Glucose, fructose and saccharose	7.4 ± 0.1	5.8 ± 0.1	1.2 ± 0.1	6.5 ± 0.1	2.1 ± 0.2	1.2 ± 0.1
Hemicellulose, starch and pectinic sugars	45.7 ± 0.9	47.7 ± 0.9	20.3 ± 0.3	15.8 ± 0.4	21.8 ± 0.4	32.9 ± 0.5
Cellulose	3.5 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.3	0.5 ± 0.1	6.4 ± 0.3	17.5 ± 0.1	14.7 ± 0.5
Lignin	12.1 ± 0.1	4.7 ± 0.2	74.1 ± 1.3	7.5 ± 0.2	49.5 ± 0.9	48.5 ± 0.3
Ashes	8.3 ± 0.2	1.7 ± 0.2	0.5 ± 0.1	3.2 ± 0.3	1.8 ± 0.3	2.3 ± 0.2
Extractives*	20.7 ± 0.5	34.0 ± 0.9	3.4 ± 0.1	10.8 ± 0.2	1.0 ± 0.2	0.4 ± 0.1

*gums, resins, waxes, etc.

Table 2.

Chemical composition of raw oils extracted from renewable biomass.

Raw oils	Pepper residues	Avocado seeds	Palm seeds	Nance seeds
Acid value (mg KOH/g)	10.9 ± 0.6	13.1 ± 0.9	1.3 ± 0.4	14.2 ± 0.6
Saponifiable lipids (% wt)	75.2 ± 0.3	16.8 ± 0.9	89.9 ± 1.6	56.8 ± 2.6
Fatty Acids (FAs) profile				
Caprylic acid (C8:0)	-	-	6.3 ± 0.4	-
Capric acid (C10:0)	-	-	5.8 ± 0.2	-
Lauric acid (C12:0)	-	-	49.7 ± 0.8	0.2
Myristic acid (C14:0)	0.6 ± 0.1	1.1 ± 0.3	14.4 ± 0.2	0.1
Palmitoleic acid (C16:1)	1.0 ± 0.1	2.1 ± 0.2	0.1	0.2
Palmitic acid (C16:0)	13.4 ± 0.1	17.1 ± 0.6	7.6 ± 0.2	11.2 ± 0.6
Oleic acid (C18:1) and Linoleic acid (C18:2)	80.4 ± 0.2	69.4 ± 1.3	13.5 ± 1.0	83.2 ± 0.8
Stearic acid (C18:0)	3.2 ± 0.1	10.3 ± 1.2	2.6 ± 0.1	5.1 ± 0.2
Other acids	1.4 ± 0.4	-	-	-
AMW (g/mol)	280.8 ± 0.1	276.4 ± 0.3	216.7 ± 0.3	278.6 ± 0.2

Table 3.

Heavy metal adsorption capacity for biochar adsorbents and commercial activated carbons.

Adsorbents	Adsorption capacity for metals (mg/g)							References
	Pb	Cu	Cr	Hg	Cd	Ni	Zn	
Biochar								
Avocado seeds	21.8	13.2	-	-	10.2	17.8	3.4	[69]
Coconut shells	-	-	-	-	-	5.9	60.4	[70]
	-	-	-	-	93.4	-	-	[71]
Flamboyant pods	27.1	-	-	-	-	6.0	-	[72]
	-	-	16.1	-	-	-	-	[73]
Orange peel	-	4.9	-	-	-	-	-	[74]
	-	-	-	-	-	6.0	5.2	[75]
Corn straw	-	12.5	-	-	-	-	11.0	[76]
Olive pomace	-	5.1	-	-	-	-	-	[74]
Rice husk	-	4.6	-	-	-	-	-	[74]
	2.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	[77]
Soybean stalk	-	-	-	0.7	-	-	-	[78]
Pecan shells	-	9.5	-	-	-	-	-	[79]
	7.5	12.1	-	-	7.0	1.4	-	[80]
Peanut shells	-	25.4	27.9	-	-	-	-	[81]
Apricot stones	22.8	24.0	29.3	-	33.6	27.2	-	[82]
Commercial activated carbon								
Norit PK 1–3	-	36.7	-	-	-	-	20.8	[83]
Purolite AC 20	37.8	24.9	-	-	33.3	-	23.3	[84]
Coal (CABOT)	29.0	-	-	-	-	6.2	8.6	[85]
Coal (Nacalai)	16.1	-	-	-	-	2.2	0.6	[85]
Filtrisorb F400	2.9	-	-	-	-	-	11.2	[86]
Carbon black	-	-	33.2	-	-	-	-	[87]